

Depression-related Risk Factors and their Association with Suicidal Ideation among College Students

Randhir Singh¹ and Satyander²

Govt. College for Women, Hisar, Haryana¹

Department of Applied Psychology, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar, Haryana²

Suicide is a major population health concern, and one of the most prevalent causes of death in nearly all parts of the world and depression has always been a major risk factor in development and persistence of suicidal ideation, yet despite the existing body of knowledge; there is a need to conduct further studies on the same to help in clarifying the same as well as to inform effective prevention strategies, particularly in high-risk groups, such as college students. The aim of the present experiment was to investigate the connection between depression and suicidal ideation in college students and a sample of 240 students in government colleges in Hisar (120 males and 120 females) was used to test the levels of depression and suicidal ideation using standardized psychological assessment instruments, that is, the Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II) and the Suicidal Ideation Scale. The results showed that there was a statistically significant positive relationship between depression and suicidal ideation, which suggests that greater levels of depressive symptoms are linked to greater suicidal ideation among college students; the results offer valuable information on the psychosocial variables affecting suicidal ideation in young adults and emphasize that early psychological interventions and enhanced mental health support networks could help reduce suicide risk among college students.

Keywords: Depression, suicidal ideation, college students, mental health, risk factors

Adolescence is a sensitive stage of development whereby major physical, emotional and social changes occur and are of key concern in determining the identity, behaviour and psychosocial adaptation of an individual (Shahrom, 2007; Mohamed, 2005). In this phase, the emotional reactivity, stress and internal conflict are likely to be heightened by the rapid hormonal changes that come with puberty, thus making them more vulnerable to identity crisis and social adaptation problems as first suggested by Stanley (1904). Such developmental issues can be expressed in various forms of social issues as per Hamzah (2003) theorizes it as falling out of accepted societal, cultural and religious norms (Bakar, 2010). Out of these issues, one has become suicidal ideation, which has become a very serious concern, particularly in adolescents and college students, as they are usually exposed to academic stress, interpersonal issues, and stressors of transition (Juhnke et al., 2011). Worryingly, suicide is among the top causes of death among young people aged between 15 and 24 years old after accidents and homicide (Anderson & Smith, 2005; Schwartz, 2006). The issue is particularly acute in educational institutions, where the rates of suicidal ideation and

attempts were regularly high (Barrios et al., 2000; Silverman et al., 1997). The literature recognises a multitude of risk factors that can result in suicidal ideation and behaviour, such as family history of suicide, substance abuse, depression, hopelessness, interpersonal conflicts, and delinquent tendencies (Connell & Meyer, 1991; Furr et al., 2001; Kisch et al., 2005; Langhinrichsen-Rohling et al.,) Depression is one of the most frequently considered contributing factors to suicidal ideation among them, but there is empirical evidence that depression does not inevitably result in suicidal behaviour, leading to the conclusion that other moderating and mediating factors such as psychosocial dysfunction, environmental stressors, and behavioural problems are involved (Thompson et al., 2006; Reinherz et al., 2006). This emphasizes the complexity of suicidal ideation and the need to consider a wider set of psychological and social determinants. It is clear that suicidal ideation is still very common among college students, so it is imperative to conduct further studies on its demographic and psychological predictors to be able to implement effective prevention and intervention measures (Drum et al., 2009). As an example, Garlow et al. (2008) examined first-year college students and discovered that depressive symptoms were strongly linked to the suicidal ideation, and the level of depression was significantly related to the probability of suicidal ideation. Likewise, a study by Ladi-Akinyemi et al. (2023) among undergraduate students in the universities of Lagos state found prevalence rates of 22.5 and 21.6 of depression and suicidal ideation, respectively, and statistically significant correlation between the two variables. These results also confirm the essential interconnection between depression and suicidal thoughts among youth groups. Although there is an increasing literature on the topic of suicidal ideation among college students, the literature is relative in terms of research that specifically examines suicidal behavior in relation to depression among specific populations and situations. In this way, the given

Author Note

¹Randhir Singh, Assistant Professor, Govt. College for Women Hisar, Haryana

²Satyander, Research Scholar, Department of Applied Psychology Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar Haryana

E-mail: satyam.mathur48@gmail.com

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Randhir Singh, Assistant Professor, Govt. College for Women Hisar, Haryana

E-mail: randhirmathur94@gmail.com

study will address this gap by investigating the relationship between depression and suicidal ideation among college students and becoming a part of the overall understanding of psychosocial mechanisms involved in these events and assisting in the development of special mental health interventions.

Method

Participants

The study population consisted of undergraduate students enrolled in colleges in Hisar city of Haryana, India. A total sample of 240 participants were selected using stratified random sampling to ensure balanced gender representation, comprising 120 male and 120 female students.

Measures

In the current research, a series of standardized and researcher-developed tools were used to gather pertinent data. To begin with, the researcher developed a Socio-Demographic Questionnaire to gain some general background data about the participants such as age and gender that are key factors in comprehending how demographics affect depression and suicidal thoughts.

Second, the Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II) which was developed by Beck, Steer, and Brown (1996) was employed to determine the extent of the depressive symptoms among the respondents. The BDI-II is a well-tested self-report measure comprising 21 items that are rated using a 4-point Likert scale of 0-3, with 0 indicating low levels of symptom severity and 3- highest levels of symptom severity. The total score will show the general degree of depression with high scores being more severe symptoms of depression. The scale has also shown a high internal consistency with an alpha coefficient of Cronbach reported to be 0.91, which means that it has high reliability.

Third, Suicidal Ideation Scale (SIS) was used to assess the occurrence and severity of suicidal ideation. It is a self-report measure that has 25 items, rated under a 5-point scale, to reflect the different levels of suicidal ideation. Of these 21 of them are positively worded and 4 are negatively worded and need reverse scoring. Psychometric properties of the SIS have proved to be satisfactory with an internal consistency of 0.81 and a test-retest reliability coefficient of 0.78 meaning that the tool is suitable in research studies to measure suicidal ideation.

Procedure

The authorities of the selected colleges of Hisar city formally gave their consent to the study before data collection. The participants were contacted in their individual classrooms and informed about the purpose, goals and importance of the study. They were assured that it was all voluntary and they could withdraw at any point with no consequences. Informed consent was done through writing to all participants prior to the administration of the instruments. The questionnaires were conducted in a group to enhance convenience and controlled environment, during regular class time under the supervision of the researcher to handle any questions, and standardization in the administration. The participants were asked to respond to the questions with utmost honesty and they were promised of the anonymity and confidentiality of their answers. The average time that the participants needed to fill out all the questionnaires was about 20-30 minutes. Once completed, the responses were tallied and

examined to ensure they were complete. When conducting the study, the high standards of ethics were adhered to, and the encompassed data was not disclosed to any third parties, no data was shared in any way except to serve the purposes of the academic and research.

Statistical Analysis

The SPSS software was used to conduct the analysis of the data, and both descriptive and inferential statistics were applied. Mean, standard deviation and frequency distributions were calculated as descriptive statistics to summarize demographic features and the scale scores. The association between the depressions and suicidal ideations among the participants was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Moreover, independent samples t-test was performed to examine the gender differences with regard to depression and suicidal ideation scores. All inferential analyses were to be statistically significant with a $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

To determine the relationship between suicidal ideation and depression, the current study was carried out on a sample of 240 undergraduates students selected in different government colleges in Hisar, Haryana, India. The sample was gender balanced, consisting of 120 males (50) and 120 females (50) and the age of the participants was in the range of 18 years to 23 years (see Table 1). Table 1 showed the distribution of frequency and percentage of the sample in terms of age, sex and residential background. In terms of age, most of the participants, 132 (55%), were in the 18-19 years age group, and the rest, 102 (42.5%), were in the 20-21 years age group with only 6 participants (2.5) being in the 22-23 years age bracket. This distribution means that the majority of the respondents were at the beginning of undergraduate studies.

Table 1

Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Undergraduate Students (N= 240)

Variables		Frequency	Percent
Age	18-19	132	55 %
	20-21	102	42.5 %
	22-23	6	2.5 %
Gender	Male	120	50 %
	Female	120	50 %
Residence background	Rural	120	50 %
	Urban	120	50 %

Gender wise, the sample was balanced: 120 individuals of both sexes (50:50) which guaranteed the representation of both genders and allowed drawing significant conclusions between groups. In terms of the residential background, the proportions of the respondents (50 each) are equal, with 120 residents of rural locations and 120 residents of the urban areas. This equal ratio of rural and urban students gives a well-rounded view and makes the results better applicable to other residential environments.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of the Undergraduate Students

Variables	Mean	SD	N
Suicidal Ideation	57.36	15.70	240
Depression	14.54	10.61	240

Table 2 represented the descriptive statistics of suicidal ideation and depression in the undergraduate students. The scores showed that the mean of the suicidal ideation score was 57.36 with the standard deviation of 15.70, which implies that there was an average level of variability in the suicidal ideation scores of the participants. Likewise, the average depressive rating was established as 14.54 with a standard deviation of 10.61, which depicts a variation in the depressive symptoms among the sample. These results give a general idea of the central tendency and dispersion of the suicidal ideation and depression scores of the 240 undergraduate students who participated in the research. Table 3 depicted the relationship between suicidal ideation and depression amongst undergraduate students. Results showed that there is statistically significant positive correlation between suicidal ideation and depression ($r = 0.562, p < 0.01$). This observation implies that the more depression a college student experiences, the greater the suicidal ideation he experiences, making depression one of the psychological components largely related to suicidal ideation. The direction and the strength of this relationship are also in line with the existing literature meaning that depression is a significant risk factor to the development of suicidal ideation and possibly suicidal behavior. The same results were also reported in the previous studies (Yen et al., 2003; Ferdowshi, 2016; Singh & Joshi, 2008; Park & Park, 2017) which also found a significant positive correlation between depressive symptoms and suicidal thoughts in the young adult population and student population.

Table 3

Correlation between Suicidal Ideation and Depression (N=240)

Variables	Depression
Suicidal Ideation	.562**

Note. ** Correlation is significant at < 0.01 level

The findings of the current research also showed that depression can lead to undesirable cognitive trends, such as negative attitudes towards self, others and future, which are generally linked to heightened susceptibility to suicidal thoughts. Depressed students might not be able to control their feelings and they might even develop hopelessness and helplessness and hence maladaptive thinking and reduced conviction that they can change their situation. These emotional and mental issues can predispose a person to irrational or negative thinking and therefore they might be more prone to thoughts of suicide. Such a close connection demonstrates that when considering suicidal ideation, particularly among stressed out college students who are also stressed by school, it is worth considering the psychological issues that stress, anxiety, and mood shifts can bring about. The results implied that detection and intervention strategies towards early alleviation of depressive symptoms should be used to prevent the development of suicidal ideation. Moreover, more studies need to be conducted to understand the intricate interaction between depression and other variables that can contribute to the emergence of suicidal thoughts and behaviors. Further studies on these relationships can aid in developing focused mental health intervention and prevention measures, which might eventually minimize the risk of self-harm and suicidal ideation in college students.

Conclusion

The current research paper aimed to investigate the connection

between depression and suicidal ideation in undergraduate students and the empirical data show that there is indeed a significant positive correlation between the two. To put it simply, a student that reported more instances of depressive symptoms also had a higher chance of having thoughts of suicide, which makes depression one of the primary psychological risk factors in the given population. This connection is more comprehensible in terms of university life that can be regarded as a time when a person experiences a great change. Students have to adapt to new academic demands, social contexts, and individual demands. When unmet, they may cause emotional distress, anxiety and depression when these needs are overwhelming or not well handled. Based on these results, it is important that schools and colleges assume an active and holistic stance in student mental health. Early identification and prompt intervention can be achieved through regular screening programs, availability of counseling services and awareness campaigns. Furthermore, the support provided to students in the campus setting, where students have no qualms about discussing their plight, may be particularly instrumental in alleviating stigma and promoting the help-seeking behavior. In general, the study highlights the critical importance of the combined use of mental health interventions that help lower suicidal thoughts and enhance the overall well-being of undergraduate students.

References

- Agerbo, E., Nordentoft, M., & Mortensen, P. B. (2002). Familial, psychiatric, and socioeconomic risk factors for suicide in young people: Nested case-control study. *BMJ*, *325*(7355), 74. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.325.7355.74>
- Barrios, L. C., Everett, S. A., Simon, T. R., & Brener, N. D. (2000). Suicide ideation among US college students: Associations with other injury risk behaviors. *Journal of American College Health*, *48*(5), 229-233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07448480009599309>
- Bakar, M.A. (2010). *Social problems in higher education institutions: Causes and solutions*. Kuala Lumpur: Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka.
- Centers for Disease Control & Prevention (CDC) (2012a). *Web-based Injury Statistics Query and Reporting System (WISQARS)*. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/injury/wisqars/index.html>
- Connell, C. M., & Meyer, R. G. (1991). The relationship of self-esteem, depression, and hopelessness to suicide ideation in college students. *Journal of College Student Development*, *32*, 266-274.
- Cooper, J., Appleby, L., & Amos, T. (2002). Life events preceding suicide by young people. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, *37*, 271-275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s001270200002>
- Drum, D. J., Brownson, C., Denmark, A. B., & Smith, S. E. (2009). New data on the nature of suicidal crises in college students: Shifting the paradigm. *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*, *40*(3), 213-222. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0014465>
- Esposito-Smythers, C., & Spirito, A. (2004). Adolescent substance use and suicidal behavior: A review with implications for treatment research. *Alcoholism: Clinical and Experimental Research*, *28*(5 Suppl), 77S-88S. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.ALC.0000127417.99752.27>
- Ferdowshi, N. (2016). Suicidal ideation in relation to depression, loneliness and hopelessness among university students. *Dhaka University Journal of Biological Sciences*, *25*(1), 57-64.
- Foster, T., Gillespie, K., & McClelland, R. (1999). Risk factors for suicide independent of DSM-III-R axis I disorder: Case-control psychological autopsy study in Northern Ireland. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, *175*(2), 175-179. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.175.2.175>
- Furr, S. R., Westefeld, J. S., McConnell, G. N., & Jenkins, J. M. (2001). Suicide and depression among college students: A decade later. *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*, *32*(1), 97-100. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0735-7028.32.1.97>
- Garlow, S. J., Rosenberg, J., Moore, J. D., Haas, A. P., Koestner, B., Hendin, H., & Nemeroff, C. B. (2008). Depression, desperation, and suicidal ideation in college students: Results from the American foundation for suicide prevention college screening project at emory university. *Depression and Anxiety*, *25*(6), 482-488. <https://doi.org/10.1002/da.20321>
- Hamzah, A. (2003). *Social problems among youth: Issues and implications*. Kuala Lumpur: University of Malaya Press.

- Juhnke, G. A., Granello, P. F., & Granello, D. H. (2011). *Suicide, self-injury, and violence in the schools: Assessment, prevention, and intervention strategies*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Kisch, J., Leino, E. V., & Silverman, M. M. (2005). Aspects of suicidal behavior, depression, and treatment in college students: Results from the Spring 2000 National College Health Assessment Survey. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 35(1), 313. <https://doi.org/10.1521/suli.35.1.3.59263>
- Konick, L. C., & Gutierrez, P. M. (2005). Testing a model of suicide ideation in college students. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 35(2), 181-192. <https://doi.org/10.1521/suli.35.2.181.62875>
- Ladi-Akinyemi, T. W., Okpue, A. P., Onigbinde, O. A., Okafor, I. P., Akodu, B., & Odeyemi, K. (2023). Depression and suicidal ideation among undergraduates in state tertiary institutions in Lagos Nigeria. *PLoS One*, 18(4), e0284955. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0284955>
- Langhinrichsen-Rohling, J., Arata, C. M., Bowers, D., O'Brien, N., & Morgan, A. (2004). Suicidal behavior, negative affect, gender, and delinquency in college students. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 34(3), 255-266. <https://doi.org/10.1521/suli.34.3.255.35445>
- Mohamed, M.N. (2005). *Psychological development across lifespan*. Kuala Lumpur: University of Malaya Press.
- Mazza, J. J., & Reynolds, W. M. (2001). An investigation of psychosocial correlates of hopelessness in adolescence. *Journal of Clinical Child Psychology*, 30(3), 439-449. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15374424JCCP3003_14
- Park, Y., & Park, Y. (2017). Effects of depression, self-esteem, and social support on suicidal ideation in college students. *Child Health Nursing Research*, 23(1), 111-116. <https://doi.org/10.4094/chnr.2017.23.1.111>
- Shahrom, M.H. (2007). *Adolescent development: Theory and issues*. Kuala Lumpur: Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka.
- Silverman, M. M., Meyer, P. M., Sloane, F., Raffel, M., & Pratt, D. M. (1997). The Big Ten Student Suicide Study: A 10-year study of suicides on Midwestern University campuses. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 27(3), 285-303. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1943-278X.1997.tb00413.x>
- Singh, R., & Joshi, H. (2008). Suicidal ideation in relation to depression, life stress and personality among college students. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 34(2), 259-265.
- Stanley, G. S. (1904). *Adolescence: Its psychology and its relations to physiology, anthropology, sociology, sex, crime, religion, and education* (Vol. 1 & 2). New York: D. Appleton & Company.
- Thompson, M. P., Ho, C. H., & Kingree, J. B. (2007). Prospective associations between delinquency and suicidal behaviors in a nationally representative sample. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 40(3), 232-237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2006.09.002>
- Thompson, M. P., Kingree, J. B., & Ho, C. H. (2006). Associations between delinquency and suicidal behaviors in a nationally representative sample of adolescents. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 36(1), 57-64. <https://doi.org/10.1521/suli.2006.36.1.57>
- Verona, E., Sachs-Ericsson, N., & Joiner, T. E. (2004). Suicide attempts associated with externalizing psychopathology in an epidemiological sample. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 161(3), 444-451. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.161.3.444>
- Yen, S., Shea, M.T., Pagno, M., Sanislow, C.A., & Grilo, C.M. (2003). Axis I and axis II disorders as predictors of prospective suicide attempts: findings from the collaborative longitudinal personality disorders study. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 112, 375-381.

Received November 15, 2025

Revision received December 3, 2025

Accepted December 6, 2025